

Supplementary Material S4.- Scatterplots showing the relationships between Scarabaeinae species richness in Mediterranean and Macaronesian islands and the different continuous or dummy predictor variables. Only those statistically significant variables are shown (see Table 1). Red broken lines represent the linear or quadratic fitted functions. The size of the dots in the case of dummy variables is proportional to the number of cases with the same values.









